

Kinetics of thermal dehydration and decomposition of hydrated chlorides of some 3d transition metals (Mn-Cu series). Part-IV. Dehydration and decomposition of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

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The kinetics of dehydration of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been studied by isothermal method in air and by non-isothermal method in air as well as in flowing nitrogen atmosphere. While in air (or self-generated atmosphere) the dehydration apparently takes place in single step, in nitrogen atmosphere two steps, corresponding to the losses of about 1.46 and 0.48 moles of H_2O , can be identified in the TG curves. Whereas in static air three-dimensional diffusion (D3 or D4 model) appears to be the best fit mechanistic model, in nitrogen atmosphere the three-dimensional progress of the reaction phase boundary (R3) followed by the first order decay of partially dehydrated porous particles (F1) appear to be the best fit models for the two steps of dehydration. When the hydrated salt is calcined at temperature above 450° , rapid dehydration renders the material porous and therefore, subsequent dechlorination also follows first order decay law (F1). Generally, there is a broad agreement in mechanistic model as well as in Arrhenius parameters between isothermal and non-isothermal methods of dehydration.

The thermal dehydration behavior of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and the kinetics of the different steps of dehydration have been studied by non-isothermal method^{1,2}. It is now well-established that like $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ the dehydration of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ takes place in three distinct steps with the loss of 4, 1 and 1 moles of H_2O respectively¹. But, in the case of dehydration of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ the two individual steps of dehydration cannot be clearly distinguished either in DTA or in TG curves³. In the case of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ the dehydration takes place in a single step^{4,5}. This suggests that the dehydration behavior of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is somewhat intermediate between dihydrates of CoCl_2 and CuCl_2 . Therefore, the study of the kinetics of dehydration of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is expected to throw some light on the nature of bonding of H_2O molecules with increase in atomic number of the metal ion.

Results and discussion

Non-isothermal dehydration and decomposition in air :

Fig. 1 illustrates typical simultaneous TG/DTA traces of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in static air and in flowing N_2 atmosphere at $10^\circ/\text{min}$ and $8^\circ/\text{min}$ respectively. The data obtained at other heating rates have been summarized in Tables 1 and 2. It can be seen from the figure that water (moisture) present in the sample in excess of dihydrate is removed at very low temperature ($55\text{--}75^\circ$) with the appearance of a broad and weak endothermic peak. This is followed by a wide plateau

Fig. 1. Typical examples of simultaneous TG/DTA of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in air and under flowing nitrogen environment at $10^\circ/\text{min}$ and $8^\circ/\text{min}$ respectively. The shaded area under the DTA peak in air is used for the estimation of heat of dehydration.

region until the major dehydration step begins at tempera-

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Table 1. Simultaneous TG/DTA results at different heating rates for the dehydration and decomposition of NiCl₂·2H₂O in static air

Heating rate °C/min	Initial loss of extra water		Major step of dehydration of dihydrate salt			Decomposition of anhydrous salt	
	Temp. range of broad DTA peak °C	Moles of H ₂ O lost (% mass loss)	Temp. range (T _i – T _c) ^a °C	DTA peak temp.	Moles of H ₂ O lost (% mass loss)	Temp. range (T _i – T _c) ^a °C	Mass loss (%)
5	55–60	0.16 (1.71)	160–257	183, 211 and 240	2.0 (21.67)	430–690	30.42
8	56–70	0.44 (4.60)	165–270	188, 217 and 245	2.0 (21.86)	440–705	31.60
10	55–75	0.22 (2.35)	167–265	190, 225 and 251	2.0 (21.80)	440–750	29.70
15	57–71	0.25 (2.68)	162–300	195, 230	1.98 (21.46)	450–790	26.43

^aT_i = temperature of inception and T_c = temperature of completion of endothermic DTA peak.

ture around 160° and ends at 257–300° depending upon the heating rate employed (see, Table 1). In this temperature range (160–300°) three endothermic peaks appear within a broad single peak. The first peak at 183–195° is rather sharp, but does not correspond to any significant mass loss. Indeed, the peak corresponds almost to the beginning of the major dehydration step.

The two subsequent DTA peaks (2nd and 3rd) though relatively weak but are distinct and appear in the temperature ranges 211–230° and 240–260° respectively. It has been observed in our earlier work² on the simultaneous DTA/TG of NiCl₂·6H₂O that the first (185–295°) and the third (240–260°) peaks appear in all cases, irrespective of the model of the TA instruments used. However, the second or the middle peak is poorly resolved in the simultaneous TG/DTA of NiCl₂·6H₂O. Since the temperature of the three endothermic peaks in the present work on dihydrate salt increase with increase in heating rate, it is difficult to attribute any one of the three peaks to phase change. Even then, we believe that one of them, possibly the first one, is due to the melting of dihydrate.

Subsequent to complete dehydration, the anhydrous salt remains stable at least up to 430°. Above this temperature, the decomposition occurs initially slowly and becomes rapid at temperature above 570° (see, Fig. 1). The completion of decomposition is also characterized by the attainment of plateau region at 690–800° depending upon heating rate with an average mass loss of 29.54% (Table 1). Since the TG curve does not show any evidence of the uptake of water vapour from the ambient atmosphere, dechlorination in the presence of air is the most likely mechanism for the formation of NiO as the final product as follows :

Since the loss of chlorine is related to the uptake of oxygen the true loss is obtained by subtracting the mass gain due to oxygen (9.66%) from the calculated loss of Cl₂ (39.08%). The value (29.42%) is very close to that found experimentally as shown in Table 1. However, the total mass loss after due correction for oxygen uptake (49.23%) is little less than that found experimentally in TG curve. This is possibly because some dehydrochlorination might take place along with dechlorination reaction.

Dehydration in nitrogen atmosphere :

Fig. 1 shows a typical example of simultaneous TG/DTA of the dehydration of NiCl₂·2H₂O in nitrogen atmosphere. It can be seen that there is a qualitative difference in the TG/DTA curves of the sample under the two different environments. The loss of extra moisture i.e., in excess of dihydrate takes place with a small endothermic peak around 57°. The subsequent endothermic peak at 139–143° does not correspond to any change in the TG curve, suggesting the occurrence of physical change which is not observed in static air. This is followed by the major dehydration which takes place in the temperature range 145–220° with peak temperature lying between 187° and 198° depending upon heating rate. This coincides with the first endothermic peak for dehydration in air. This is followed by a weak shoulder at about 225°. Unlike dehydration in air, no endothermic peak after the first major peak is observed. A similar thermoanalytical behavior has also been observed by Mohamed and Halawy⁵ in the DTA curves of the dehydration of NiCl₂·6H₂O in N₂ environment. At 10°/min the dehydration of dihydrate is represented by a single broad

Table 2. Simultaneous TG/DTA at different heating rates for the dehydration of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in flowing nitrogen environment

Heating rate °C/min	Initial loss of extra water		Second endo effect without mass loss		Major step of dehydration of the dihydrate salt			
	DTA peak temp. °C	Moles of H_2O lost (% mass loss)	Temp. range ($T_i - T_e$) ^a °C	DTA peak temp. °C	Temp. range ($T_i - T_e$) ^a °C	DTA peak temp. °C	Moles of H_2O lost (%) mass loss)	
							1st step	2nd step
4	57	0.28 (3.00)	128–144	139	144–198	187.0	1.47 (16.0)	0.46 (5.0)
6	56	0.26 (2.85)	130–146.5	141	146.5–206	192.5	1.43 (15.5)	0.48 (5.2)
8	60	0.30 (3.23)	135–150	143.5	150–220	198.5	1.43 (15.6)	0.50 (5.4)

^a T_i = temperature of inception and T_e = temperature of completion of endothermic DTA peak.

endo peak at 202° and a shoulder at 245°. But at 20°/min an additional peak at 197° appears and the subsequent peaks shift to 215° and 260° respectively, possibly representing the loss of the last two moles of H_2O .

In contrast to dehydration in air, two different steps of mass loss can be distinguished from the TG curves in flowing N_2 environment. Fig. 1 shows a distinct break after the loss of 2.9 mg of H_2O corresponding to 1.43 moles of H_2O and the remaining 1 mg of water corresponding to 0.5 mole of H_2O is lost rather slowly with increase in temperature. Similar break in TG curve is also observed for other two heating rates in N_2 atmosphere and the results are given in Table 2.

Kinetics of non-isothermal dehydration of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$:

As followed in the previous papers the kinetics of non-isothermal dehydration of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been studied by the isoconversion method⁶. Initially, the fractional dehydration (α) was calculated by selecting inception temperatures for the dehydration of dihydrate at different heating rates after the loss of initial moisture. This led to considerable differences in the inception temperature and as a result, isoconversion plots show deviation from linear behavior. It may be noted that dehydration of dihydrate salt begins at about 13% of total mass loss, but to be on the safe side we have taken $\alpha = 0.15$ as the beginning of rapid loss of water from dihydrate. On this basis, isoconversion plots were made from $\alpha = 0.15$ to 0.95. The activation energy (E) values obtained from the slopes of the straight lines comprising all the four heating rates decrease from 99.0 kJ mol^{-1} to 53.0 kJ mol^{-1} with increase in α (see, Table 3). The mean E value (72.2 kJ mol^{-1}) is used to calculate the reduced time (θ , min) for at least three heating rates (5, 8 and 10°/min) by following the same procedure as described earlier. The mean θ values given in Table 4 are used to calculate real or isothermal time t for different values of α at three or four temperatures within the reaction regime. The α - t data for the dehydration of dihydrate in air are found to

Table 3. Activation energy (E) values at different levels of fractional dehydration (α) as obtained from isoconversion plots for the thermal dehydration of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in air and in nitrogen atmosphere

Fraction dehydrated (α)	Dehydration in air kJ mol^{-1}	Dehydration in flowing N_2 atmosphere	
		First stage loss of 1.46 moles of H_2O	Second stage loss of 0.48 moles of H_2O
0.05	91.03	–	–
0.10	–	100.13	120.16
0.15	98.31	–	–
0.20	99.22	96.86	113.79
0.30	85.57	99.22	113.79
0.40	80.11	107.42	105.60
0.50	69.18	98.31	113.79
0.60	65.54	109.24	120.16
0.70	61.89	109.24	109.24
0.80	54.62	101.95	105.60
0.90	54.62	104.68	–
0.95	53.16	109.24	–
Mean	72.22	101.00	112.77

follow diffusion controlled (D3 and D4) mechanistic models best. But considering little higher correlation coefficient value as well as its more realistic nature D4 is taken as appropriate mechanism. The Arrhenius parameters are given in Table 5.

It has already been shown in TG curve in Fig. 1 that dehydration in nitrogen atmosphere takes place in two steps. Consequently, two different sets of α - T curves are generated for the two steps of dehydration. The two sets of α - T curves also led to the generation of two sets of isoconversion plots. A good linear relationship with almost similar slope values can be obtained over a wide range of α values comprising the three heating rates (4–8°/min). Following the same procedure as stated above the E and mean θ values have been calculated and the data are shown in Tables 3 and 4 respectively. The α - t data sets calculated at different

Table 4. Average values of reduced time (θ) calculated from three heating rates using the mean E values given in Table 3 for the dehydration of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Fraction dehydrated (α)	Dehydration in air $\times 10^8$ min	Dehydration in flowing N_2 atmosphere	
		First stage loss of 1.46 moles of H_2O $\times 10^{12}$ min	Second stage loss of 0.48 moles of H_2O $\times 10^{12}$ min
0.05	–	1.166	–
0.10	–	1.635	1.410
0.15	1.334	–	–
0.20	1.697	2.880	1.849
0.30	2.409	4.205	1.957
0.40	3.471	5.763	2.310
0.50	4.853	7.444	2.744
0.60	6.803	9.290	3.320
0.70	9.656	11.340	4.014
0.80	14.300	13.980	5.042
0.90	21.360	17.600	–
0.95	27.890	20.330	–

temperatures within the reaction regime from mean θ values have been used to test the best fit model for dehydra-

tion mechanism in N_2 atmosphere.

As expected, two different mechanisms are involved in the two different stages of dehydration in N_2 atmosphere. The loss of first 1.46 moles of H_2O follows both two (R2) and three (R3) dimensional progress of reactant/product phase boundary models. However, considering higher value of R^2 and also its more realistic physical picture R3 is chosen as the appropriate model. The loss of balance 0.48 moles fit F1 model ($R^2 = 0.9963$) best. The results suggest that the dehydration is possibly initiated at the surface resulting in rapid diffusion of H_2O molecules and relatively slower growth of product phase and therefore the progress reaction boundary towards the core. The Arrhenius parameters are given in Table 5.

Kinetics of isothermal dehydration of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$:

An attempt has been made to study the kinetics of dehydration of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by using the isothermal mode of the TA instrument i.e. by holding the temperature constant and recording the mass loss as function of time, obtained from chart speed. However, there is a perennial problem associated with this method. To raise the temperature quickly to the desired value it is necessary to use high heat-

Table 5. Kinetic models and Arrhenius parameters derived from α -time data at different temperatures using the isoconversion method and also those obtained from actual isothermal experiments for the dehydration and decomposition of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Nature of reaction step	Average θ range (min)	α range	Temp. range (K)	Kinetic model (code)	Correlation coefficient (R^2)	Arrhenius parameters		
						E kJ mol^{-1}	$\log A$ min^{-1}	Correlation coefficient (R^2)
<i>Dehydration in static air</i>								
Dehydration incl. initial loss of H_2O	(1.334–27.890) $\times 10^{-8}$	0.15–0.95	473–503	D3	0.9975	71.53	6.10	0.9970
–	–	–	–	D4	0.9983	73.26	6.08	0.9998
Actual isothermal expt.	–	0–0.40	423–453	D3	0.9952	55.66	4.21	0.9975
–	–	–	–	ZLT	0.9940	60.38	4.73	0.9894
<i>Dehydration in flowing nitrogen atmosphere</i>								
1st step loss of 1.46 moles of H_2O	(1.166–2.033) $\times 10^{-12}$	0.05–0.95	440–460	R3	0.9990	101.29	10.53	1.0
2nd step loss of 0.48 moles of H_2O	(1.410–5.042) $\times 10^{-12}$	0.10–0.80	470–490	F1	0.9962	112.20	11.56	1.0
<i>Decomposition of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$</i>								
Actual isothermal experiment	–	0–0.50	723–873	F1	0.9950	71.20	2.62	0.9988
–	–	–	–	R3	0.9900	68.90	2.37	0.9984

ing rate and therefore high input of energy to the furnace. This makes the temperature to shoot up much above the desired value and this needs some time to cool down and stabilize at the set value. On the other hand, if low heating rate is used it needs much longer time to attain the desired temperature. In both the situations, considerable extent of reaction already takes place before the measurement of mass loss begins at constant temperature. However, using 15–20°/min of heating rate, it has been possible to carry out some isothermal experiments on the dehydration of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 150, 160 and 180° even though some losses take place before the measurement begins.

Fig. 2a shows the variation of fractional mass loss with time at the above three temperatures. The fractional mass loss is obtained by dividing the observed loss with the calculated loss of total water present in the sample. It may be observed from Fig. 2a that the rate is deceleratory from the

Fig. 2. (a) Plot of fraction dehydrated (α) as function of time and temperature. (b) Application of D₃ and ZLT models to α -time data (for model equations see Ref. 8).

very beginning indicating that it is controlled by either diffusion or progress of reaction phase boundary. An attempt has been made to fit the α - t data to various mechanistic models. It has been observed that both Jander's (D₃) and Zuravlev, Lesokhin and Templ'man (ZLT) equations fit the data with almost equal goodness (Fig. 2b) suggesting that diffusion is the slower process unlike non-isothermal method. But the applicability of D₃ as a mechanistic model at least up to 40% conversion appears questionable. This is because one of the basic assumptions in the D₃ model is that reaction area does not change with time. While this is true for flat surface, for spherical symmetry this holds good only at very low conversion. At high conversion the reaction surface area can not remain constant for particles with spherical symmetry. The reason for fitting D₃ model up to $\alpha = 0.4$ is possibly because the difference in density between the reactant and the product is very little so that no change in volume occurs with the progress of dehydration. Similar mechanism has also been observed for the dehydration of ferric chloride hydrate⁷.

The applicability of ZLT model to the initial stage of dehydration of $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been demonstrated⁸. When a solid-state reaction is accompanied by the evolution of gaseous product the reactivity is suppressed within the solid matrix. Consequently, the reaction tends to be initiated from the surface because of higher diffusivity of gaseous product. In such a case the progress of the reactant/product interface from the periphery to the center becomes rate-controlling. However, if extensive nucleation occurs within the solid matrix, the product phase grows rapidly and diffusion becomes slow and therefore tends to be rate-controlling. The ZLT model of solid-state reaction takes into account both diffusion and decreasing area of the reaction interface (spherical symmetry) which is related to activity of the unreacted material. As the correlation coefficient of Arrhenius plot based on ZLT model is lower than that of D₃ model (see, Table 5), the latter is accepted as more appropriate in this case.

Isothermal decomposition of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$:

It has been observed that isoconversion plots for the decomposition of nickel(II) chloride do not yield good linear behavior over a wide range of fractional decomposition. Therefore, isothermal method has been used for the study of the kinetics of decomposition of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Fig. 3 shows the plot of percent decomposed as function of time and temperature. Chemical analysis of the product obtained after calcinations at 600° for one hour shows that the amount of nickel insolubilized or the decrease in the amount of chloride content are 51.4 and 47.5% respectively with re-

Fig. 3. Plot of % loss of HCl during the decomposition of dihydrate salt vs time of heating at different temperatures.

spect to their contents in the hydrated salt. This shows that an average of 50.5% of NiCl₂ is still present in the undecomposed state. It may, therefore, be inferred from Fig. 3 that the total theoretical loss of chlorine is about 40% with respect to original sample mass i.e. dihydrate salt used. This value is much higher than the average value of about 29.8% found from TGA data of anhydrous salt (see, Table 1). Therefore, the isothermal decomposition of NiCl₂.2H₂O at temperature above 450° is different from that of the decomposition of anhydrous salt under non-isothermal condition. The proposed reaction scheme for the decomposition of the dihydrate salt is as follows :

On adding, the overall reaction is given by

Although the formation of basic chloride of nickel has been identified by XRD studies the presence of oxychloride has not yet been identified in the present work¹. However, the formation of similar oxychloride has been suggested during the decomposition of the chlorides of Cu^{II}⁹ and Pb^{II}¹⁰.

From the above overall reaction the calculated loss of Cl and HCl is found to be 43.45% from which the gain in mass due to uptake of oxygen (4.83%) when subtracted gives 39.62% as the maximum mass loss. This is in agreement with the results of chemical analysis. Further, the loss of water calculated from the overall reaction is 15.54% without any correction for mass gain as the release of water is not related to the oxygen uptake. This is in conformity with the observed loss of 14.7% during isothermal heating. Therefore, the fractional loss (α) of Cl + HCl is obtained by dividing experimentally found loss with the calculated loss of 39.62%.

An attempt has been made to fit the α -time plot to appropriate mechanistic model. It can be seen from Fig. 4 that both F1 and R3 models fit the data with equal goodness. In the first place this suggests that the rate of diffusion of Cl or HCl is rather high because of sufficient cracks, fissures etc. created by the rapidly escaping water vapour in the first one or two minutes of heating at high temperature. In such a situation the rates of both nucleation and growth of product phase become slow the latter appears to be slower process.

Fig. 4. Application of F1 and R3 models to the fraction decomposed (a) vs heating time (t) data.

Heat of dehydration of NiCl₂.2H₂O :

From the area covered by the composite peaks in the DTA trace at 10°/min in air (see, Fig. 1) an attempt has been made to estimate the heat of dehydration of NiCl₂.2H₂O. The value (ΔH_{reac}) comes out to be 53.81 kJ mol⁻¹ for the entire dehydration process i.e. for the loss of two moles of water. However, ΔH_{reac} values calculated from the last two steps of the dehydration of NiCl₂.6H₂O from

the relevant DTA peaks are about 54.0 and 41.0 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively^{1,11}. Therefore, the ΔH_{reac} value obtained in the present work corresponds to the loss of first mole of water. Interestingly, this value is very close to the activation energy value (55 kJ mol⁻¹) obtained by the isothermal method of dehydration.

Experimental

Materials : About 10 g of freshly procured "Extrapure" grade (E. Merck, India) NiCl₂.6H₂O crystals was ground in an agate mortar until the entire powder passes through 150 μm sieve. The powder was taken in a silica dish, dried first at low temperature (50–60°) for 1h and then at 95 \pm 5° until the color of the salt changed to yellow. During this process a small quantity (about 0.2 g) of dried sample was taken out intermittently (2-3 times) and analyzed for Ni, Cl and H₂O by difference. When the composition reaches very close to NiCl₂.2H₂O the material was taken out from the oven, transferred to a well-stoppered sample bottle and stored in a desiccator.

Methods : Simultaneous TG/DTA experiments were carried out in a Shimadzu (Japan) Thermal Analyzer (model DT-40). While dehydration in static air was carried out using platinum crucibles, in flowing N₂ atmosphere alumina micro-crucibles were used. Isothermal decomposition of NiCl₂.H₂O was carried out according to the procedure described in the preceding paper¹².

Analysis : Nickel was estimated by titrating with 0.01 M EDTA solution using murexide as indicator at pH 10. Chloride

was estimated by titrating with standard (0.01M) AgNO₃ solution in the presence of K₂CrO₄ as indicator. Water content was estimated by difference from 100%.

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